

Sexual Dimorphism of Corpus Callosum Occurs in Human Foetuses

M. Pramila Padmini, B. Narasinga Rao

Department of Anatomy, Maharajah's Institute of Medical Sciences, Nellimarla-535217

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Abstract:

Sexual dimorphism in human corpus callosum is controversial, and only a limited number of studies have been done on foetuses. Corpus callosum of 50 foetal brains, 25 male and 24 female were studied however, one foetus with undifferentiated sex, was excluded from the present study. The crown rump length (CRL) and the brain weight of these foetuses ranged from 5 to 39 cm and 10 to 550 gm. Brain was divided into two equal halves by median section after fixation. The length of the corpus callosum, pre-callosal and post-callosal lengths, were measured on the medial aspect of each cerebral hemisphere. The thickness of splenium was measured in the sagittal section. The brain weight increased with increase in the CRL length in all the foetuses. The average length of the corpus callosum was more in males than in females. The z test value was 1.3871, which is not significant. The thickness of splenium was more in females than male. The z test value was 2.28, which is highly significant. Sex difference was not observed in any of the other parameters.

Key Words: Cerebral hemispheres, Corpus callosum, Dimorphism, Splenium.

Introduction:

The corpus callosum (Latin: tough body), also known as the callosal commissure, is a wide, flat bundle of neural fibers beneath the cortex in the eutherian brain at the longitudinal fissure. It connects the left and right cerebral hemispheres and facilitates inter-hemispheric communication. It is the largest white matter structure in the brain, consisting of 200-250 million contralateral axonal projections (http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Corpus_callosum). Several sex-specific genes not dependent on sex steroids are expressed differently in male and female human brains. Structural sex difference begins recognizable by 2 years of age and include size and shape of the corpus callosum, certain hypothalamic nuclei and the gonadotropin feedback response to estradiol. There are disputed claims about the difference in the size of the human corpus callosum in men and women and its relationship to gender differences in human behaviour and cognition (Gupta et al, 2011). Sexual dimorphism in human corpus callosum is controversial, and only a limited number of studies have been done on foetuses. Therefore, the present study was taken up.

Materials and Methods:

Fifty foetuses were obtained from hospital of Maharaja's Institute of Medical Sciences, local

government and private hospitals after getting necessary permissions from the concerned parents. The gestational age of the aborted foetuses ranged from 10 to 40 weeks. Crown Rump (CR) length was measured, and from it, gestational age was computed (Hamilton et al, 1972).

A median section of the brain was cut after fixation and the following measurements of the corpus callosum were taken on the medial aspect of each cerebral hemisphere. Even though, 50 foetal brains were obtained, one brain having a flat hemisphere was excluded from this study. Out of the remaining 49 brains, corpus callosum measurements of 5 female foetal brains and 5 male fetal brains could not be recorded due to damage to parts of the corpus callosum and hence, their measurements are not shown in the data and marked as asterisk (*) in table I and II. Following measurements of remaining 78 sagittal sections of 39 brains (20 male and 19 female) were taken:

1. Length of the corpus callosum (CCL)-The distance between rostrum and splenium of corpus callosum,
2. Pre-callosal length was measured from genu to frontal pole
3. Post-callosal length was measured from splenium to occipital pole
4. Thickness of splenium was measured by a graduated metal scale from the inner surface of the corpus callosum, that is from ventricular cavity at the level of splenium to the summit of the outer surface of splenium where there is the maximum thickness, in the sagittal section.

Corresponding Author: Dr. M. Pramila Padmini, Department of Anatomy, Maharajah's Institute of Medical Sciences, Nellimarla-535217

Phone No.: +91 - 9949519333

E-mail : mini141@yahoo.com

Fig. I: Corpus callosum in female fetuses: a) 12 wks, b) 22 wks, c) 29 wks & d) 40 wks.

Observations:

During the first trimester in females, the corpus callosum is very small measuring a length of 12 mm with pre-callosal and post-callosal length of 6 mm (Fig.Ia). During mid weeks of second trimester it measured approximately thrice the length of first trimester that is 34 mm (Fig.Ib). By the end of second trimester, it reached a length of 44 mm. At 29 wks of gestation, the corpus callosum measured a length of 41 mm (Fig. I c). By 40 wks gestation, it increased to a length of 70 mm with pre and post callosal length of 30 and 41 mm respectively (Fig. Id). The thickness of the splenium of the corpus callosum increased from 3 to 10 mm in female foetuses.

Male foetuses of first trimester could not be procured, therefore, the observations were made from second trimester onwards. In males, the corpus callosum measured a length of 18 mm with pre and post-callosal length of 10 and 11 mm respectively (Fig. IIa). It measured 32 mm at 22 and 23wks of gestation (Fig.IIb) and the pre and post-callosal lengths were 16 and 22 mm respectively. At 30 wks of gestation, the corpus callosum measured 43 mm (Fig.IIc). By 39 wks, it increased to a length of 68 mm with pre and post callosal length of 25 and 38 mm respectively (Fig.IId). The thickness of the splenium of the corpus callosum increased from 3 mm to 7 mm in male foetuses.

Table I: Length of corpus callosum, pre and post callosal lengths and thickness of splenium in female brains.

Age (wks)	Length of Corpus callosum(mm)	Pre-callosal length (mm)	Post-callosal length (mm)	Thickness of Splenium (mm)
11	*	*	*	*
12	12	06	06	03
12	12	06	06	03
13	12	07	06	03
17	*	*	*	*
17	16	10	15	04
17	17	07	11	04
18	22	09	15	06
18	26	08	16	06
22	34	14	16	06
22	30	15	17	06
23	35	15	20	07
24	39	13	24	06
24	44	18	21	07
25	*	*	*	*
25	*	*	*	*
26	40	15	32	07
26	43	17	29	08
27	*	*	*	*
29	41	17	28	07
37	60	28	38	07
37	58	23	35	08
40	69	19	44	10
40	70	3	41	10

* Indicate parts of the brain tissue of fetuses that has been damaged

The repeated weeks in the table I & II indicate the number of foetuses in that particular gestation. The average length of the corpus callosum is

Fig. II: Corpus callosum in male fetuses: a) 16 wks, b) 22 wks, c) 30 wks & d) 39 wks

Table II: Length of corpus callosum pre and post callosal lengths and thickness of splenium in male fetuses.

Age (wks)	Length of Corpus callosum (mm)	Pre-callosal Length (mm)	Post-callosal Length (mm)	Thickness of Splenium (mm)
14	*	*	*	*
16	18	10	11	03
19	30	14	18	03
20	31	15	18	03
22	32	16	18	04
23	32	16	22	03
25	35	13	32	04
25	*	*	*	*
25	39	13	33	04
27	45	15	27	04
28	39	18	30	05
29	*	*	*	*
30	43	21	31	04
31	48	19	30	04
31	50	20	36	05
33	55	23	37	05
34	50	28	30	06
34	62	26	40	05
36	*	*	*	*
36	*	*	*	*
38	60	30	32	05
39	58	30	36	06
39	62	25	45	07
40	62	21	41	06
40	68	25	38	07

* Indicate parts of the brain tissue of fetuses that has been damaged. more in males than in females. The z test value is 1.3871, which is not significant. The thickness of splenium has increased in females than in males. The z test value is 2.28, which is highly significant (Table III).

Table III: Z-test value for length of corpus callosum and thickness of splenium between male and female corpus callosum:

	Length of corpus callosum		Thickness of corpus callosum	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
Mean	42.55	35.7894	4.7619	6
Standard Deviation	12.0104	17.7273	1.3380	2.0976
Standard Error	4.8736		0.5429	
z-value	1.3871		2.2803	

Discussion:

Shape and size of the human foetal corpus callosum of a relatively racially homogeneous southern Indian population were studied. Significant absolute increase occurred in callosal length in female foetuses with the increase in gestational age (Koshi et al, 1997). The present findings are in agreement with the observations of above workers.

Bishop & Wahlsten (1997) indicated that, on an average, males have larger brains than females and that the average size of their corpus callosum is larger. The findings of the present study showed that the average length of the corpus callosum was 42.55mm in males which was more as compared to females (35.78 mm). The thickness of splenium is more in females than males. Dubb et al (2003) demonstrated that females had a larger splenium than males (p<0.001 uncorrected

for multiple comparisons) while males possessed a larger genu. The findings of the present study are in agreement with the above observations. DeLacoste-Utamsing & Holloway (1982) observed that the female splenium is more bulbous and larger than the male counterpart. Since peristriate, parietal, and superior temporal fibers course through the splenium, this finding could be related to possible gender differences in the degree of lateralization for visuospatial functions. Occipital fibres also pass through splenium (Dougherty et al, 2005). Larger splenium implies a larger number of fibers, and that the number of interhemispheric fibers correlates inversely with lateralization of function (Weis et al, 1989). In the present study, absolute increase occurred in the length of the corpus callosum in females (Table I) than in males (Table II).

In the present study the pre-callosal and post-callosal measurements are more in females than males, which could be due to rapid increase in the antero-posterior axis.

The present findings suggesting sexual dimorphism of human corpus callosum, raise the possibility that prenatal sex hormones may play a role in determining callosal development. Corpus callosum, being the major structure connecting both the hemispheres, is likely to be affected by the physiological as well as pathological changes occurring in the cortical and sub cortical regions of brain (Gupta et al, 2011). Therefore, different sub regions of the corpus callosum may be affected depending upon the region of the brain involved, as almost all the fibres connecting opposite hemispheric regions pass through specific callosal sub regions. Therefore, any alteration in the corpus callosum morphology, may give a clue towards the time of occurrence of specific disease process. A knowledge of the corpus callosum morphology, the gender and age related changes, may be helpful in providing baseline data for the diagnosis of a disease and its progression (Gupta et al, 2011).

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